

The COREnect Editorial

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Dear Readers of our COREnect newsletter,

We are excited about the outcome of the first step towards a significant delivery of the project. We shall give the EC and our society an insight into the main areas of technology that are essential for delivering 5G and 6G solutions of the future. COREnect and its amazing team of nearly 100 experts has identified the following technology areas within the three Expert Groups:

Expert Group 1 - Compute/Storage

- Processor Instruction Set Architecture (ISA)
- Storage & Memory
- Multi-Processor Systems-on-Chip
- Operating Systems Platforms
- Systems Architecture
- Semiconductor Technology

Expert Group 2 - Connect & Communicate

- Radio access networks (RAN)
- Consumer grade connectivity
- Industrial grade connectivity
- Datacenters

Expert Group 3 - Sense & Power

- Sensor Processing
- Power management
- Accelerators
- User Interface
- Core Process Technologies
- System & Component Architectures

We have broken down the requirements within each area and identified their key technologies. Based on this, COREnect will identify the main “punch lines” of necessary action for future research efforts. Additionally, a wide list of further topics to watch out for and spend research effort gives insight into the position of Europe in the semiconductor roadmap for being able to deliver future cellular communications products.

Thanks a lot to all who have such vivid and inspirational input, and the key team driving the COREnect!